

CIPIS, Marcelo. **Entre tantos**. Illustrations Marcelo Cipis. São Paulo: Brasil, 2018.

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

The author, illustrator and plastic artist Marcelo Cipis has worked with illustration for magazines, newspapers and books since 1977. In 1994 he was awarded the Jabuti best cover award for *Like Water for Chocolate*. In *Entre tantos* (Among Many) he recovers, with very funny images and unusual scenes, the coincidences of everyday life and how small and circular this universe is: everything ends where it started. The world is immense, however tiny and full of twists that lead us to the coincidences of everyday life.

Keywords: Images. Daily. Routines.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.